

BIOTECHNOLOGICAL RECYCLING AND RECOVERY OF METALS FROM SECONDARY RAW MATERIALS THROUGH BIOGENIC SYNTHESIS OF NANOPARTICLES

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ABSTRACT. The waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) is an important secondary source for renewable extraction of valuable metals and raw materials. The mineral biotechnologies are promising alternative to the current industrial chemical technologies for waste treatment, which are often accompanied with negative environmental impact. Here we report a systematic biotechnological strategy for recycling, recovering and extraction of metals from WEEE as biogenic formed nanoparticles. The process is based on two general steps – bioleaching (through autotrophic/heterotrophic bacteria), and extraction from the effluent as biosynthesised nanoscale materials. The obtained analytical data revealed that copper was bioleached in the form of nanoparticles, the efficiency being more than 90 %, which was the highest achieved value in comparison with the other metals. The recovered content of gold was less than 50 %, but the efforts for improvement of microbial leaching efficiency of Au are still in progress. The reported eco-friendly biotechnological approach enables proper implementation of new resource recovery-oriented recycling strategies with reduced risk of negative impact on nature.

Key words: biotechnological recycling, secondary raw materials, nanoparticles

Introduction

The waste of electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE), which is often referred to as electronic waste (E-waste), is discarded devices that are at the end of their exploitation life and cannot be utilised by consumers anymore (Baldé et al., 2015). WEEE is being hazardous to the environment, in particular the printed circuit boards (Ghosh et al., 2015). On the other hand, E-waste could be considered as an important secondary source of valuable and critical metals. The elemental composition of the discarded devices might be often highly variable and complex (Cui and Forsberg, 2007). However, numerous references have reported significantly higher contents of copper, iron, aluminium, and nickel, as well as lower amounts of gold, silver, and palladium (Yamane et al., 2011) than in natural ores.

The metal recovery from WEEE as a secondary source is necessary for the sustainable development of economy, for supporting the conservation of the primary sources and preventing further environmental contamination (Robinson, 2009). There is a huge number of conventional methods (particularly in the chemical and metallurgical processing sectors) for recovery of metals from secondary raw materials (Ilyas and Lee, 2014), but in recent years the research efforts have been focused on the development of environmentally friendly biotechnological treatment and recycling strategies (Nancharaiyah et al., 2015; İşildar et al., 2019). They may offer promising alternatives to the pyrometallurgical technology, because of the designed selectivity towards critical and valuable metals, lower environmental impact and cost-effectiveness (Morin et al., 2006). The bioprocessing includes various microbial techniques as bioleaching, bioreduction, biosorption, etc., in which a wide and diverse range of chemolithotrophic, heterotrophic and thermophilic microorganisms are involved (Xiang et al., 2010; Natarajan and Ting, 2014). Most of them have a high tolerance to the heavy metal toxicity (*Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans*,

Acidithiobacillus thiooxidans and *Leptospirillum ferrooxidans*). These microorganisms have been tested to mobilise base and precious metals (Cu, Fe, Ni, Zn, Au, Ag, Pt, Pd, etc.) from discarded printed circuit boards (PCB) through biochemical mobilisation mechanisms.

In this report a biotechnological strategy was developed for recycling, recovering and extraction of both critical and conventional metals as nanoparticles from WEEE. The emphasis was put on copper and gold, as well as on other metal contents from PCB.

First, the metals were bioleached in a two-steps autotrophic/heterotrophic biorecovery strategy through redoxolysis, acidolysis and complexolysis mechanisms. For that purpose the bioleaching media that contained E-waste was inoculated with cultures of chemolithotrophic acidophilic iron- and sulphur-oxidising microorganisms (İşildar et al., 2016). In this case, the biogenic sulphuric acid and ferric iron act as lixivants via respectively, acidolysis and redoxolysis bioleaching mechanisms (Bas et al., 2013). The metals were mobilised to their ionic state in the media via either acidolysis or redoxolysis. The copper was predominantly found in PCB and it was bioleached by a mixture of autotrophic iron- and sulphur oxidiser *Acidithiobacillus ferrivorans* and *Acidithiobacillus thiooxidans*. The gold was removed from WEEE by *Pseudomonas putida* at ambient temperature (Brandl, 2008).

Second, biosynthesis of nanoparticles and extraction of these metals from the concentrates was accomplished. Bacteria and fungi microorganisms are suitable for metallic nanoparticle production through secretion of NADH dependent enzymes necessary for the extracellular processes.

The mechanism for nanoparticles formation was following the designed strategy: A) Metal ions are trapped on the surface or within microbial cells (De Yoreo and Vekilov, 2003). Gold, silver and palladium ions are attracted due to the electrostatic interactions with the enzyme carboxylate groups of the negatively charged cell wall (Sneha et al., 2010). (B) The

cations are reduced by reducing agents (reductase enzymes and proteins, exopolysaccharide, and electron shuttle quinones) or precipitated as nanoparticles with different size and shapes (Singh et al., 2016). As a result, the inorganic metal residues were deposited on the surface of precipitations through adsorption or co-precipitation (Hohmann et al., 2010).

Experimental Procedures

Grinding and preparation of E-waste for bioleaching treatment

TV circuit boards and PCB were used as manufacturing scrap in our experiments. The samples were initially crushed in a rotary cutting shredder to a size of 2-3 mm and then grinded to 200-250 μm by ultracentrifugal mill (Retsch, Model ZM200 Ultra). The grinded samples were used for the further bioleaching experiments in microbiological suspension. Their metal composition was determined by chemical analysis (the concentration of iron was determined using titration with KMnO_4) and atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer AAnalyst 400). The samples contained mainly copper (19-22 %), iron (1-5 %), aluminium (1-3 %), nickel (< 1 %) and precious metals as gold, palladium and platinum in trace concentrations (< 0.001 %). Additional amount of pyrite (up to 40 g/L) was mixed with the sample as a source of iron and sulphur in order to initiate the bioleaching processes.

Metals recycling and biorecovery by cultivated microorganisms

A mixed culture of mesophilic bacteria (*A. ferrooxidans*, *L. ferrooxidans*, *A. thiooxidans*) was used for the biorecovery stage of the metals.

The microbiological suspension was grown and maintained on pyritic materials. The composition of growth media was 1.5 g/L $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 0.5 g/L $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.5 g/L KH_2PO_4 , and 0.1 g/L KCl. For the bioleaching reaction 200 mM Fe(II) was added to the culture and subcultured at pH 1.7, 30 °C. The acidithiobacillus strains were grown also in a nutrition medium containing: 2.0 g/L $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 0.25 g/L $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.1 g/L KH_2PO_4 , 0.1 g/L KCl, 8.0 g/L $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 10 g/L elemental sulphur. pH was adjusted to 2.5 by H_2SO_4 and the cultures were inoculated with 5 % growth medium and incubated at 30 °C. The residue of the first bioleaching step was collected, filtered, left to dry overnight, and sterilised before the second step.

The sterilised residue was then subjected to secondary bioleaching by adding the dried material of the first bioleaching step to cultures of cyanogenic bacteria as *Pseudomonas putida*. The cyanogenic strains were grown in nutrient broth containing: 1.0 g/L meat extract, 2.0 g/L yeast extract, 2.0 g/L peptone, and 5.0 g/L NaCl for subculturing and in glycine-supplemented medium for cyanogenic activity and bioleaching reactions. The pH of suspension was adjusted to 7.3 with 1 M NaOH. The microbial cultures were subcultured with 1% (v/v) in 100 mL growth medium in 300 mL Erlenmeyer flasks and incubated at 30 °C at a rotation speed of 150 rpm (Brunswick Innova 2000, USA).

The growth of bacteria was monitored by measuring optical density (OD) at 600 nm.

The bioleaching experiments were conducted in 250-mL Erlenmeyer shake flasks. Freshly grown and active bacterial culture (10^7 - 10^8 cells/mL) was applied as inoculum (10 mL).

Erlenmeyer flasks were placed on an orbital shaker operated at 35 °C. During the biorecovery process aliquots of 1 ml were taken and used for elemental analysis of the dissolved metals by atomic absorption spectrophotometry. pH and redox potential were also used to monitor the microbial activity.

Biosynthesis of nanoparticles from the bioleached dissolved metals

A. Primary treatment of the pregnant leach solutions (PLS) with fungus *Fusarium oxysporum*.

To accomplish the biosynthesis of nanoparticles (mainly CuS, CdS, ZnS and Au) the fungus *Fusarium oxysporum* was used, which was kindly provided by Saitama University, Japan. The fungus was cultivated at 30 °C in Petri dishes with growth nutrition medium contained 20 % potato, 2 % dextrose and 2 % agar. Four-day old fungal spores were inoculated into 500 ml flask containing 100 ml medium (0.3 % malt extract, 1.0 % glucose, 0.5 % peptone and 0.3 % yeast extract) in order to initiate the fermentation. The flask was placed in a shaker-incubator (Brunswick Innova 2000, USA) for 96 hours at 30 °C and 160 rpm.

After completing the fermentation period, the mycelia were collected through centrifugation. They were washed with MilliQ water under sterile conditions. Further these mycelia were suspended in 100 ml of solution containing recovered Cu^{2+} with concentration around 0.001 M at pH = 5.0 – 5.5. The Erlenmeyer flasks were transferred into the shaker-incubator and kept there for 96 hours at 30 °C and 160 rpm. After that the biosynthesised nanoparticles were extracted (as mentioned above CuS, CdS, ZnS and Au) by centrifugation (14700 rpm for 30 min).

B. Secondary treatment of the residue PLS with *Bacillus cereus*.

The residue media of PLS was additionally treated with *Bacillus cereus* to extract the rest of precious metals (mainly Au and trace amount of Pt or Pd).

The bacterial culture was incubated in the shaker for 24 hours at 30 °C and 160 rpm. After obtaining the microbial biomass, the medium was centrifuged and bacteria were inoculated with the residue effluents containing dissolved gold. The microsuspension was incubated at 37 °C and 200 rpm for 24 hours. The gold nanoparticles were extracted by centrifugation (14700 rpm for 30 min).

Nanoparticle characterisation

The presence of nanoparticles was confirmed by absorbance spectra (UV-VIS Jasco analytical spectrophotometer, model No V-570) and 200 kV scanning transmission electron microscope (STEM, JEOL 2010F), equipped with a field emission gun and EDX spectrometer. The solution containing Au nanoparticles has a maximum absorbance peak at 500-550 nm due to the surface plasmon resonance (SPR).

EDX elemental analysis was used to prove the presence of Cu, Cd, Zn and Au. For this aim the nanoparticles samples were freeze-dried and the obtained powder was heated up to 300 °C for 1 hour. EDX spectra were recorded under 30° specimen tilt in high angle annular dark field (HAADF) STEM mode with 1 nm scanning electron probe size to ensure improved EDX signal-to-noise ratio.

Results and Discussion

Chemical analysis of the discarded PCB

The chemical analysis of the PCB waste showed a variety of metals as presented in Table 1. The copper (Cu) concentration was the highest one (around 20 %) in the all various PCB types. Cu, iron (Fe) and aluminium (Al) were the other common elements among the assayed metals with concentrations around 3% and 4%, respectively. The mobile phones showed higher concentration of copper and gold than the other E-waste, which is due to their design and compact size. A notable variation in the concentrations of Al, Ni, Zn and Cd was determined too.

Table 1. Metal concentrations (mg/g) in the discarded PCBs

Element	Computer parts	Desktops	Mobile phones
Cu	102.3 ± 5.1	201.8 ± 9.7	229.8 ± 8.5
Al	16.3 ± 3.9	34.8 ± 2.1	9.8 ± 3.7
Fe	3.3 ± 0.1	48.8 ± 7.3	39.7 ± 2.4
Zn	0.27 ± 0.01	4.9 ± 1.1	3.7 ± 0.1
Ni	0.88 ± 0.02	2.5 ± 0.2	10.4 ± 0.8
Cd	0.11 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.01	1.1 ± 0.1
Au	0.034 ± 0.002	0.023 ± 0.001	0.335 ± 0.002

Two steps bioleaching of metals

First step – bioleaching by acidophiles microorganisms. The copper was bioleached from PCB waste with very high efficiency, which was over 90 % (as shown on Figure 1). The control experiments proved that the acidophilic microorganisms *A. thiooxidans* and *A. ferrivorans* were responsible for the mobilisation of Cu from the waste in the aqueous suspension. During the process pH of the effluent might slightly decrease.

Fig. 1. Bioleaching profile of Cu by the acidophiles

In order to mitigate the inhibitory effect of PCB on bacteria, acidophiles were first incubated in the bioleaching medium until bacterial suspension with high optical density was established. Subsequently, grinded E-waste was added to the system with fixed amount. The bacterial activity was monitored

by measuring of pH and ORP. These two parameters indicate the proceeding of acidolysis and redoxolysis mechanisms of bioleaching. In the first 24 hours the bioleaching of Cu showed a logarithmic increase trend. After that, the rate decreased, which is typically observed in the bioleaching processes. The role of acidophiles microorganisms was to catalyse the oxidation of Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺ and generate sulphuric acid. Then the biogenic produced Fe³⁺ and H₂SO₄ leached Cu⁰ contents at low pH and high ORP, according to the chemical reactions:

The oxidation reaction leads to pH increasing and ORP decreasing. This is the first reason for the decreased rate of bioleaching after the logarithmic trend. The second reason was the inhibition of microbial activity from the released toxic compounds (aromatics, phenols, polybrominated diphenyl ethers, heavy metals, etc.) from PCB.

Second step – bioleaching by cyanide producing heterotroph microorganisms. After leaching of Cu, the chemical analysis proved that significant amount of Au still remained in the residue, containing waste materials. To extract the gold components, the remaining material was treated with cyanide producing *P. putida* strains. The gold leaching by biogenic cyanide is presented on Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Au bioleaching by biogenic cyanide producing *Pseudomonas putida* from the residue waste material

By this approach, the achieved highest gold recovery in our experiment was around 30 %, but some amount of Au (15-20 %) has been mobilised during the bioleaching with acidophiles. The experiments for improvement of microbial leaching efficiency of gold are still in progress. The experiments also demonstrated a correlation between the biogenic cyanide concentration and efficiency of gold mobilisation. Stoichiometrically, it is shown on the chemical reaction below:

The consumption of cyanide might be an indication that there is another precious metal or copper, which has been not leached in the previous step. In addition, Zn, Ni and Fe form stable complexes with CN⁻. At high concentration, these metals might consume the cyanide contents and the bioleaching process of gold will be blocked. The process of cyanidation is dependent on pH and the leaching of gold is typically carried out in alkaline conditions (pH > 10.5). Therefore, the higher pH favours the metal mobilisation efficiency. Nevertheless, in the performed biotechnological experiments an optimum pH should be used in respect to the bacterial physiological requirements.

Nanoparticles synthesis by microorganisms

The obtained pregnant leach solutions with dissolved metals were finally subject to treatment with microorganisms for biogenic synthesis of nanoparticles. pH of solutions was

adjusted to pH = 5.5, and the PLS were inoculated with *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Bacillus cereus* to obtain nanoparticles containing Cu, Zn, Cd, Au, etc. As mentioned above, the microorganisms have several mechanisms for biomineralisation or formation of minerals with nano-size on their membrane. Some of the mechanisms are not yet completely understood, especially the forming of gold nanoparticles on the fungal mycelia. Probably the metal reduction occurred thanks to NADH and NADH-dependent nitrate reductase enzymes, which act as a carrier and are responsible for the electron transfer to the cation (Ahmad et al., 2002). The formation of mineral depositions containing nanoparticles on the cell walls of microorganisms was observed by transmission electron microscope, as shown on Figure 3. In the control experiment (Figure 3A) the smooth structure of the cell wall can be seen and there are no biomineral depositions, they appear on the next image (Figure 3B), which is the case of nanoparticle synthesis.

Fig. 3. Transmission electron microscopic images of (A) microorganisms used for nanoparticle synthesis as control experiment. (B) Microorganisms producing biomineralisation on their membrane envelopes. Scale bars for A and B = 1 μ m

Microscopic characterisation of the biogenic produced nanoparticles

The biosynthesis of nanoparticles was performed through a two-steps process. During the biosynthesis, the colour of the medium gradually turned to black, which was an indication of the successful biogenic synthesis of nanoparticles (or nanoscale materials). The experimental observation of colour change was significant in the primary treatment of PLS with the fungus *Fusarium oxysporum* and was due to the formed metal sulphide nanoparticles. A precipitated sample (pellet) was obtained from the microbial suspension with aim to analyse the nanoparticles size, shape and elemental composition. As shown on the dark-field STEM micrographic image on Figure 4A the nanoparticles were varying in size, but most of them have a diameter less than 10 nm. They have different shapes such as circular, triangle, or complex. In addition, most of them tend to form aggregations (it is hard to

find single dispersed nanoparticles on the image). From the STEM image it is notable that the nanoparticles differ in contrast. The reason is that they contain different metal composition. EDX analysis of the aggregation on the micrograph (Figure 4B) revealed the presence of metals as Cu, Zn, Cd (probably some amount of Ag) and Au (Loukanov et al., 2010). The X-ray peaks of platinum are close to those of gold, so probably the sample might contain some trace amount of Pt or other precious metals.

As shown in the micrographic image the nanoparticles tend to form aggregations. It is difficult to distinguish what is the chemical composition in each individual particle. The EDX spectrum includes the signal emitted from all captured objects. Based on the contrast difference we can distinguish formation of nanoparticles with different elemental composition. The lower contrast particles are built from lighter elements and the higher contrasted from a heavier one.

Fig. 4. Scanning electron microscopic characterisation of the biosynthesised nanoparticles. (A) Dark-field STEM image of nanoparticles aggregations. The nanoparticles have different contrast due to the different elemental composition. Scale bar = 10 nm (B) EDX-analysis of the aggregations. The presence of elements as Cu, Zn, Cd (probably Ag) and Au was detected in the observed sample

In addition, the chemical and physicochemical processes as reduction, precipitation, co-precipitation, and adsorption are responsible for the formation of the aggregations observed in STEM. In the current report the nanomaterials were not separated based on their chemical composition. Such separation is possible by chromatography based on their different size and weight, and this research is in progress. However, the developed environmentally friendly method enables reliable recovery and extraction of toxic metals from E-waste thanks to their transformation into nanomaterials, which are easy to precipitate and separate from the concentrate.

Conclusion

In this study, we developed versatile biotechnological state-of-art method for recycling, recovery and extraction of metals as biosynthesised nanoparticles from E-waste. It has numerous advantages as (1) potentially better environmental and eco-friendly profile, (2) easy and practical operation, (3) better cost-effectiveness, and (4) potential for future development. Such bio-based eco-technology could be developed also towards more selectivity for metals' recovery. It enables proper implementation of new resource recovery-oriented recycling strategies and may contribute to the reducing of the environmental risks associated with recycling processes of the waste electrical and electronic equipment.

Acknowledgment

This study was funded by MEXT/JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number T20K05260.

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